
Application and Challenges of Data Analytics implementing in Accounting

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Abstract:

In the technological world, Data analytics is one of the tools in the hands of professionals for analysing data. It is nothing but a subset of Business Intelligence (BI), which is itself a subset of Business Analytics (BA). Data science and Business Intelligence (BI) helps in analysing a large amount of structured data to forecast and predict the future events. After introduction of GST in 2017, there is vast growth in the work of professionals as well as businesses, hence it is the need to businessman and accountants to make use data analytics to take a better decision. Though there are various tools used in accounting like tally prime, it is advanced one with different aspects. This study is purely based on secondary data to understand the applications and to face challenges in implementing data analytics in accounting.

Keywords: *Data Analytics, Technology, Accounting, Benefits, Challenges, Implementation*

Introduction:

Data analytics is called as the Double-Edged Sword in Accounting. It has made revolution in various industries and accounting is no exception to this. Data analytics is a process which uses algorithms to extract and analyze information from large amounts of data. Accounting data analytics is a subset of this process where the information extracted comes from financial transactions, such as invoices, payments, and receipts. Accounting data analytics allows businesses to make informed decisions based on the analysis of this information.

Due to the introduction of Goods and Services Tax (GST), the enormous documentation of transactions is increased, as a result businesses are facing the problems of documentation. The task and need of professionals like, tax consultant, CAs, Auditors, Accountants are increasing

as the size or volume of business becoming large. Hence, data analytics is an emerging tool in the hands of professionals to reduce the burden of time and cost.

Data analytics gather and organise substantial amounts of data to manage demands time, discipline with a specific set of skills. A professional should have such skills with a background in data analytics. Their knowledge and experience increase an efficiency to maintain the data and extract its value. The skilled accountant with background of data analytics is the need of businesses.

The accountant or professionals use the analytics to make a decision on the basis of static data with continuous monitoring. It provides a holistic view and empowers to make more accurate and timely decisions. Generally, the accountant uses following four types for data analysis:

Types and Functions of Data Analytics

Sr. No	Type of analytics	Functions
1	Descriptive Analytics	to create reports and financial statements.
2	Diagnostic Analytics	to create dashboards that analyse completed business periods.
3	Predictive Analytics	to create models illustrating possible business results.
4	Prescriptive Analytics	come into play when developing data-backed business plans.

The descriptive analytics reveals the data regarding What's going on? While Diagnostic analytics analyses and provides data related to Why? Descriptive Analytics. The Predictive analytics anticipate the trends that influence these predictions. As same the prescriptive analytics help to accountants to create reports based on facts that can be turned into practical steps.

Tools for Data Analytics in Accounting:

An accountant should have technical expertise to achieve success with data analytics. The knowledge of programming as Python and "R" is required to develop algorithms and data models. The accountant should have knowledge of following skills to perform better. The following tools will reveal the relevance of the accounting data.

Tools for Data Analytics in Accounting

Sr. No	Tool	Nature of Company	Use in Accounting
1	Excel	Small business	creating budgets, making financial statements, and building balance sheets.
2	Tableau	mid-sized company	to represent data visually. Deal with extensive data
3	Power BI (BI + Data Visualisation)	Any Company or Business	linking with Excel, Quick books, Google Analytics, and other applications. It enables accountants to consolidate various data streams using Power BI.
4	IDEA	Any Company or Business	software designed specifically for data analytics. Data can be imported and analysed swiftly, effectively, and in a format that is easy for users to navigate.
5	A.I. and Analytics	Any Company or Business	critically assess, interpret, and formulate business plans using the provided data.

Objectives of the study:

Followings are the objectives aimed by the researcher:

1. To know the relevance of accounting and data analytics.
2. To study the tools for data analytics in accounting.
3. To understand the applications and challenges in implementing data analytics in accounting.
4. To draw a conclusion for proper implementation of data analytics.

Statement of the Problem:

In the advanced technological world, the technology like AI, Chatbot, Data analytics and knowledge is moving with hand in hand. An accountant, a tax consultant or a professional has to analyse the data effectively for business decision.

Scope of the Study:

This research paper has a wide scope as technological, professional, economical, to prosper the wings of future accounting for businesses. The application of data analytics

is necessary to achieve various benefits of technology.

Research Methodology:

This research paper is purely based on secondary data as available in journals, annual reports, government reports and websites.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The analysis and interpretation of the data is based on the following two important aspects i.e. Application of Data analytics and Challenges of Implementing Data Analytics

in Accounting as it is descriptive study and based on secondary data.

Applications of Data Analytics in Accounting:

As per the available data from Institute of Management Accountants most of the companies or finance firms have implemented data technologies for accounting and financial services. On the other hand few companies are planning to implement. The following table will reveal the status

Table No.1 Status of Implementation of Technology

Technology	Completed implementation (%)	Plan to Implement (%)
Self-service reporting	48	31
Big Data	32	35
Data Visualization	27	37
Predictive Modeling	25	33
Automation	22	42
Voice Recognition	5	20

(Source: Institute of Management Accountants)

The above table and graph indicates that 48 percent finance firms have implemented technology for self service reporting, Big data (32), Data visualization (27), Predictive Modeling (25), Automation (22) and very less in Voice recognition (5). On the other hand, some of the finance firms in the verge of implementation these technologies.

It is observed that most of companies are implementing these technologies for the application of fraud

detection, financial forecasting, Risk assessment and Audit efficiency.

The application of data analytics helps in identifying the irregular financial transitions i.e duplication of receipts or payments, unauthorised access and fraudulent claims. Further it helps to get alerts to avoid risk in financial transactions.

The finance firms also implement data analytics for analysing historical data to get future financial trends and performance.

It helps in making decisions about budgeting, investment and risk management.

financial, credit, market and operational risk. It extracts, reconciles and analyse data.

It is observed that data analytics also help in identifying and assessing various

Table No.2 Purpose of Data Analytics and Big Data

Purpose	Data Analytics (%)	Big Data (%)	Both (%)
Performance Measurement	7	26	18
Formulating Strategy	7	16	15
Research & Development	5	11	10
Product Rationalisation	5	10	8
Order fulfilment	5	5	2

(Source: Institute of Management Accountants)

It is observed that the data analytics has lesser share as compared to use of big data. Hence there is requirement to develop awareness amongst the firms to implement data analytics for effective accounting.

From the above data and graph, it is observed that most of the companies are facing the challenges in implementing data analytics. The companies may be facing the challenges like data quality, or misleading data, lack of skilled professionals in data science, statistics, and accounting, ethical factors like privacy, security and bias and implementation cost of software and training issues etc.

Conclusion:

Though Data analytics offer various opportunities for accountants to enhance their efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making capabilities, the finance firms or

companies planning to implement data analytics due to certain challenges before them. It is a need to overcome the coming challenges by improving skill and technological knowledge and know-how for effective implementation of data analytics in accounting for better services.

References:

1. AICPA (2019). Data Analytics in the Accounting Profession.
2. Deloitte (2018). The Rise of Cognitive Technologies in the Audit.
3. 3.EY (2017). How Data Analytics is Transforming the Audit.
4. Jasdeep Bhatia (2024) Accounting and Data Analytics: Types, Tools, Challenges (October 3)
5. Allied Market Research. (2020). Predictive Analytics Market by Component, Deployment Mode, Organization Size, and Industry

- Vertical: Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast, 2020–2027.
6. Deloitte. (2018). The Power of Analytics for FP&A: Connecting Data to Decision Making.
 7. PwC. (2019). Finance Effectiveness Benchmark Report 2019.
 8. Gartner. (2020). Real-Time Data: The Essential Ingredient for Modern Finance.
 9. Markets and Markets. (2020). Data Analytics Market by Component, Business Function, Deployment Mode, Organization Size, Industry Vertical, and Region - Global Forecast to 2025.
 10. One Click IT Consultancy June 19, 2024